

Grant Agreement n° 101115488

Double-Active Membranes for a sustainable CO₂ cycle
01/11/2023 – 31/10/2026

EIC Pathfinder Challenge: Carbon dioxide and Nitrogen management and valorisation

Deliverable Number	3.1
Deliverable Name	Protocol for basic and advanced characterization
Lead Beneficiary	INSTM
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date	31/07/2024
Submission Date	31/07/2024

Keywords:

Materials, characterization, physico-chemical properties, Polymers, Metal-Organic Frameworks, Photocatalysts

Abstract:This deliverable aims at setting the protocol for basic and advanced characterization of the materials synthesized in WP2, to rationally drive the choice of the best materials to be employed in the preparation in WP4 of the Mixed Matrix Membranes used for CO₂ capture and conversion.

Summary

Consortium of DAM4CO₂	2
Document History	3
Approval History	3
Introduction	4
Basic Characterization of Pristine Materials	5
Basic characterization of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) – INSTM	5
Basic characterization of soluble and insoluble Polymers – USwan, UEdin	8
Basic characterization of PhotoThermal Catalysts – ITQ-UPV, INSTM	11
Advanced Characterization of fillers for MMMs	15
Advanced Characterization of MOFs and insoluble Polymers – INSTM, CNR, USwan	15
Thermal stability of MOFs – INSTM.....	16
Adsorption properties of MOFs and insoluble polymers – INSTM, USwan	17
Investigation of structural and dynamic properties - CNR.....	21
Advanced Characterization of PhotoThermal catalysts – INSTM, ITQ-UPV, CNR	23
Investigation of photothermal catalysts surface – INSTM, ITQ-UPV	23
Redox and photoelectronic properties of photothermal catalysts – ITQ-UPV.....	27
Morphological investigation of the active phase – ITQ-UPV	29
Investigation of structural properties – CNR.....	30
Tables of ongoing Characterization experiments	32
References	37
Acknowledgements	37

Consortium of DAM4CO₂

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT	999979500
2	BEN	INSTM	CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO NAZIONALE PER LA SCIENZA E TECNOLOGIA DEI MATERIALI	IT	999991237
3	BEN	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	999864846
4	BEN	PRIMALCHIT	PRIMALCHIT SOLUTIONS	ES	892236168
5	BEN	Me-Sep	ME-SEP SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA	PL	887256382
6	BEN	USwan	SWANSEA UNIVERSITY	UK	999862033
7	BEN	UEdin	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UK	999974941

Document History

Version	Date	Contributors	Description
v1	13/06/2024	Marco Lessi (INSTM)	First draft
v1a	09/07/2024	Mariolino Carta (Uswan)	Review
v1b	05/07/2024	Hermengildo Garcia baldovi (ITQ-UPV)	Review
v1c	17/07/2024	Lucia Calucci (CNR)	Review
v1d	19/07/2024	Marco Taddei (INSTM)	Review
v1e	22/07/2024	Valentina Crocellà (INSTM)	Review
v1f	23/07/2024	Mariolino Carta (Uswan)	Review
v1g	26/07/2024	Marco Lessi (INSTM)	Review
v1h	29/07/2024	Valentina Crocellà (INSTM)	Review
v1h	29/07/2024		Sent to EB
V1i	31/07/2024	Valentina Crocellà (INSTM)	Review
V2	31/07/2024	Valentina Crocellà (INSTM) and Marco Lessi (INSTM)	Final draft

Approval History

	Name Surname	Date of Approval
WP Leader	Valentina Crocellà	29/07/2024
Coordinator*	Alessio Fuoco	31/07/2024

*on behalf of the Executive Board

Introduction

WP3 is devoted to the characterization at different levels of the materials synthesized in WP2.

The physico-chemical characterization of materials is a relevant domain for a variety of fields, including selective adsorption and catalysis. For this reason, starting from a basic characterization step to assess the success of the syntheses, WP3 evolves towards a targeted multi-technique characterization approach to shed light on the physico-chemical features and on the adsorption/catalytic properties of the pristine materials used for Mixed Matrix Membranes (MMMs) assembly. In particular, the main role of WP3 is to rationally drive the choice of the best materials (*Task 3.1*) to be employed in the preparation of the MMMs (WP4) used for CO₂ capture and conversion. In a second moment, the unique multi-technique characterization approach of WP3 will investigate the structure-property relationships of materials, identifying the active sites and disclosing the adsorption/reaction mechanisms (*Tasks 3.2 and 3.3*), further helping the development of the best MMMs for CO₂ capture and conversion.

At the beginning of the project, it is mandatory to plan a **protocol for basic and advanced characterization** that could become a milestone in the pristine materials characterization (matrices, adsorbents and catalysts) that could be routinely applied to the following generations of materials produced by WP2, to help and speed up the selection of the best fillers and matrices for MMMs production.

The present **Deliverable (D3.1)** will define the above-mentioned protocol of characterization, derived from the experimental activities of *Tasks from 3.1a to 3.1f* in the first 9 months of the project. For the sake of clarity, the document will be divided in different sections:

- 1) *Basic Characterization of Pristine Materials*: immediately after the synthesis, all materials will be investigated by means of different **basic characterization techniques**. This characterization step is useful for evaluating the success of the synthesis and for assessing whether the materials deserve to be investigated in subsequent advanced characterization steps. The basic characterization section will be further divided into three sub-sections related to the three categories of materials synthesized in WP2: *Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)*, *Soluble and insoluble Polymers* and *Photocatalysts*.
- 2) *Advanced Characterization of Pristine Materials*: after the preliminary standard characterization, the successfully synthesized materials will undergo an **advanced characterization step** to deeply investigate their intimate properties and really understand if they deserve to be employed in the MMMs production. The advanced characterization section will be further divided into two main sections: *adsorbents (MOFs or polymers)* and *photocatalysts*.
- 3) *Table of Characterizations*: the table will give an **overview of the characterization** (both basic and advanced) **carried out until month 9** on the different DAM4CO₂ materials synthesized by WP2, as possible candidates for MMMs preparation. **In these tables, the materials synthesized as benchmarks will be listed as well.** Indeed, especially in the catalytic section, the understanding of photocatalysts to be used as references is crucial for the development of other catalysts based of non-critical raw materials.

Basic Characterization of Pristine Materials

Basic characterization of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) – INSTM

MOFs, to be employed as fillers for MMMs, are synthesized by INSTM in “green” conditions, using as precursors non-critical metals and non-environmentally hazardous organic linkers and exploiting water or alcohols as solvents. The overall synthesis process is detailed in *Deliverable 2.1 of WP2*.

After the synthesis, a work-up procedure is carried out, usually with the same solvents employed during the synthesis process. The materials are washed several times under stirring at room temperature, to remove any unreacted reagents or by-products and then dried overnight in oven, usually at 80 °C, to finally recover the powder.

Once dried, MOFs are studied with different experimental techniques for a basic characterization step to assess the success of the synthesis procedure.

The following basic characterization protocol is carried out on all synthesized MOFs:

- a) **Experimental Technique:** Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) is performed in Bragg-Brentano geometry using the Cu K α radiation either with a PANalytical X’PERT PRO diffractometer, PW3050 goniometer, equipped with an X’Celerator detector, or with a Rigaku Miniflex 600-C equipped with a D/teX Ultra silicon strip detector.

Target: this technique is used to confirm the phase purity and to estimate crystallite size, based on the broadening of the diffraction profile (the sharper the Bragg reflections, the larger the crystallite size).

Example of a PXRD pattern of a MOF (Ca-squarate)

Figure 1. Experimental and theoretical PXRD patterns of Ca-squarate.

The PXRD pattern of the sample is compared with the calculated one (Figure 1), based on the crystal structure deposited in the Cambridge Structural Database (refcode: FIRVEH)¹. The above reported analysis proves that the desired crystalline phase is obtained with a high crystallinity, as revealed by the sharp Bragg reflections.

- b) **Experimental Technique:** Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) is carried out under a mixed N_2/O_2 80:20 atmosphere, either with a NETZSCH STA 449 Jupiter instrument or with a TA Instrument Thermo-balance model Q5000IR.

Target: this technique is carried out to study the thermal stability of the materials, to identify mass losses related to solvent removal from the pores and/or decomposition of the organic part of the framework.

Example of TGA experiment of a MOF (Ca-squarate)

Figure 2. TGA curve of Ca-squarate.

The TGA profile (Figure 2) reveals four mass losses occurring up to 700 °C. Assuming the formula $[Ca(H_2O)(C_4O_4)] \cdot 1.4H_2O$, the following considerations can be made:

- The mass loss occurring below 100 °C is associated with the desorption of 1.4 molecules of physisorbed water per formula unit;
- The mass loss occurring between 200 and 300 °C is associated with the release of 1 molecule of coordinated water per formula unit;
- The mass loss occurring between 400 and 500 °C is associated with the decarboxylation of the squarate linker to afford $CaCO_3$;
- The mass loss occurring between 550 and 600 °C is associated with the decarboxylation of $CaCO_3$ to CaO .

These results are in agreement with the literature.²

- c) **Experimental Technique:** Inductively Coupled plasma - Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) is carried out with Vertex 70 model (Varian-700 ES). Before the experiment, a known amount of sample is suspended in aqua-regia or similar acidic solution and heated to 80 °C until full disaggregation of the solid particles.

Target: this technique is used to investigate the metal content of the materials. This analysis provides the metal ions concentration within MOFs and consequentially a confirmation of the chemical formula.

- d) **Experimental Technique:** Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is performed with a JEOL 7800F FEG SEM. The samples are sputtered with platinum prior the analysis.

Target: this technique is employed to study the morphology and particle size of the samples. This last feature is fundamental, since it will affect the dispersion of the filler in the matrix to prepare the MMM.

Example of SEM analysis of a MOF (Ca-squarate)

Figure 3. SEM image of Ca-squarate.

The SEM analysis (Figure 3) reveals the presence of crystallites with rod-like morphology and size in the range of 10-50 µm, in agreement with the literature ²

- e) **Experimental Technique:** N₂ Adsorption/Desorption at 77 K (N₂@77K) is performed with a Micromeritics 3Flex sorption analyzer in the 0-1 p/p₀ range. Before each measurement, samples (in powder form) are activated to remove the physisorbed species, by heating the materials under vacuum at a specific temperature (evaluated by the TGA results).

Target: this technique is employed to investigate the textural properties of materials (specific surface area, SSA, Cumulative Pore Volume, CPV and Pore Size Distribution, PSD). Measurements with N₂ at low T are feasible only if the probe can access the porous structure of the MOF. If that is not the case, other adsorptive will be evaluated for textural properties evaluation (see advanced characterization paragraph). For CPV/PSD evaluation of microporous materials, the N₂ adsorption isotherm at 77 K must be collected by acquiring at least 30 points below 0.01 of p/p₀.

Example of N₂ isotherms at 77 K of a MOF (Zn-UTSA-16)

Figure 4. N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherms at 77 K of Zn-UTSA-16 samples with different particles morphology. The table reports the SSA computed for the two materials.

The adsorption/desorption isotherms of Zn-UTSA-16 samples are acquired with N_2 at 77 K in the 0-1 p/p_0 range (Figure 4) after activation at 363 K overnight under vacuum. The collected isotherms are of Type Ia (IUPAC classification)³ below 0.5 of relative pressure, as expected for microporous MOFs. The hysteresis loop above 0.6 of p/p_0 is related to the capillary condensation in interparticle voids. The BET SSA reported in the table are calculated through the BET equation, by applying the Rouquerol consistency criteria to the adsorption branch of the isotherm.

Figure 5. PSD and CPV curves of Zn-UTSA-16 obtained by NL-DFT from N_2 isotherm at 77 K.

PSD and CPV of a Zn-UTSA-16 sample (Figure 5) are evaluated by applying the Non-Local Density Functional Theory (NL-DFT) to the adsorption branch of the isotherm. For each experimental adsorption curve, the kernel of isotherms with the best fit is selected. The PSD curve exhibits a bimodal distribution in the 0.5-1.5 nm range and a CPV of $\sim 0.2 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ STP in the micropores range. All data perfectly agree with the literature.⁴

If the NL-DFT model does not allow us to obtain a good fit between theoretical and experimental isotherms, the t-plot method could be alternatively employed for the evaluation of the Micropore Volume (MV) and/or the Micropore Area (MA). In this case, however, no information on the PSD can be obtained.

Basic characterization of soluble and insoluble Polymers – USwan, UEdin

The soluble polymers prepared in the initial phase of the DAM4CO₂ project will serve as the matrix for Mixed Matrix Membranes (MMMs), while the insoluble polymers will be used as fillers. All materials require structural, porosity, and thermal characterizations before they can be sent for advanced analysis by INSTM and CNR partners and used to produce the necessary MMMs.

Particularly for the soluble polymers, bulk synthesis is essential, as they typically constitute 80-90% of each MMM. Therefore, large-scale production is required, and the overall synthesis process is detailed in *Deliverable 2.1 of WP2*. Conversely, the organic fillers, which act as additives in MMMs, can be prepared on a smaller scale since they account for only 10-20% of the related MMMs. Despite the difference in scale, the basic characterization techniques for both soluble and insoluble polymers

will be the same. Additionally, fundamental techniques for the structural assignment of precursors and monomers are necessary, and these methods are outlined below.

The basic characterization of monomers and polymers produced at USwan and UEdin consist of the following:

- a) **Experimental Technique:** Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy (^1H and ^{13}C) is carried out on a BRUKER Avance 500 NMR instrument at 500 MHz for ^1H NMR, 125 MHz for ^{13}C NMR.

Target: this technique is commonly used for the assessment of structures of monomers and polymers. In a typical experiment, the spectrum, measured in deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3 , $\sim 10 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) as the solvent, shows the broad peaks typically related to polymer chains.

- b) **Experimental Technique:** Infrared spectroscopy (IR) is carried out with a BRUKER, Alpha P instrument. All samples are measured by attenuated total reflection (ATR) and measured in the solid state. The positions of the absorption bands are given in wavenumbers (cm^{-1}) and are measured in the $3600 - 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral range. In a typical experiment, a background is measured to subtract the noise coming from air and CO_2 . Then a small amount of solid sample ($\sim 5\text{-}10 \text{ mg}$) is placed in the ATR and compressed to achieve the best possible absorption.

Target: this technique is complementary to NMR for the assignment of the correct chemical structures of monomers and polymers. In the case of polymers, we look for the peaks of the main functional groups and we compared them with the literature and/or with our previously prepared materials.

Example of ^1H NMR and IR of a polymer (PIM-1)

Figure 6. ^1H NMR (A) and IR (B) spectra of PIM-1.

Typical IR and NMR spectra are shown in Figure 6 for PIM-1, which show broad peaks related to slow relaxation times of the polymeric chains in the ^1H NMR (A) and the position of the main functional groups on IR (B). The assignment for both ^1H NMR and IR are perfectly in line with expectations.⁵

- c) **Experimental Technique:** Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) is measured on a Perkin Elmer simultaneous Thermal Analyser STA 6000 device.

Target: this experimental technique is carried out for the assessment of the thermal stability of polymers. In a typical experiment, an appropriate amount of sample (typically ~ 10 mg) is weighed into a ceramic crucible, then it is equilibrated for 20 minutes at 25°C and heated at a rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ from 25 to 1000°C under a nitrogen flow of 20 mL min^{-1} .

Example of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of 6FDA-DAM

The instrument records the mass loss occurring with the increase of the temperature and time, build a TGA profile like the one shown below. The analysis in Figure 7 shows that the polymer, in this example the polyimide 6FDA-DAM, is highly thermally stable, with a decomposition temperature the starts at $\sim 510^\circ\text{C}$, with a mass loss of $\sim 45\%$ at $\sim 950^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 7. TG curve of 6FDA-DAM

- d) **Experimental Technique:** N_2 Adsorption/Desorption at 77 K ($\text{N}_2@77\text{K}$) in the 0-1 p/p_0 range are made using an Anton Paar Nova600 sorption analyser. The samples are tested as a powder, weighed (roughly 100-150 mg) in an Anton Paar adsorption cell and outgassed under vacuum for 8 hours between 353-393 K, depending on the stability of the polymer (evaluated by the TGA curves).

Target: this technique is employed to investigate the textural properties of materials (specific surface area, SSA, Cumulative Pore Volume, CPV and Pore Size Distribution, PSD). Measurements with N_2 at low T are feasible only if the probe can access the porous structure of the MOF. If that is not the case, other adsorptive will be evaluated for textural properties evaluation (see advanced characterization paragraph). The isotherm curve of the measurement of a polymer sample is built with around 25 points in adsorption and 18 in desorption up to 1 bar. In addition, for CPV/PSD evaluation, the N_2 adsorption isotherm at 77 K must be collected by acquiring at least 30 points below 0.01 of p/p_0 .

Example of N₂ isotherms at 77 K of a MOF (PIM-1)

Figure 8. N₂ adsorption (black) - desorption (red) isotherms at 77 K of PIM-1.

The N₂ isotherms at 77 K of PIM-1 in the 0-1 p/p₀ range (Figure 8), after activation at 393 K for 8 h in vacuum, resulted in a Type Ia curve, according to the IUPAC definition,³ with a sharp uptake at very low partial pressure and with a relatively pronounced hysteresis in desorption, in which the desorption branch of the isotherm does not close to the adsorption branch, generated by possible swelling phenomena occurring upon N₂ adsorption. The BET SSA calculated at p/p₀ < 0.1 is ~784 m²g⁻¹, whereas the pore volume calculated at p/p₀ = 0.98585 is 7.160*10⁻¹ cm³g⁻¹. The volumetric data on PIM-1 agree with the literature.⁶

Basic characterization of PhotoThermal Catalysts – ITQ-UPV, INSTM

On the catalytic side, DAM4CO₂ aims at developing PhotoThermal Catalysts (PhotoCat) for CO₂ conversion in two reaction stages: Reverse water gas shift and Fischer-Tropsch (CO₂ -> CO + H₂O/CO₂+H₂ -> C₂₊ - C₁₀). Regardless of the catalytic process, after the synthesis of each Photocat made by ITQ-UPV partner (whose synthesis procedure is detailed in *Deliverable 2.1 of WP2*), a standard physico-chemical characterization step with different experimental techniques is followed to verify that the synthesis is carried out successfully and provide relevant characteristics of the catalysts.

The protocol of characterization is applied also to materials synthesized (or directly employed because commercially available) as benchmarks. Indeed, the understanding of reference photocatalysts is crucial for the development of other catalysts based of non-critical raw materials. The following basic characterization protocol is adopted to all synthesized (or commercial) PhotoCat:

- Experimental Technique:** *Infrared spectroscopy (IR)* is carried out on a Nexus 8700 FTIR spectrophotometer in ATR mode. Before the measurement, the sample is prepared by drying it at 100 °C for at least 3 hours to remove physisorbed water. The warm sample is directly placed in the sample holder and measured.

Target: this technique helps to identify functional groups, by comparing them with the literature and/or with our previously prepared materials.

- b) **Experimental Technique:** Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) is carried out in Bragg-Brentano geometry using a Shimadzu XRD-7000 diffractometer with a Cu K α radiation ($\lambda=1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) source. The sample holder is selected depending on the amount of sample to measure. With amount higher than 100 mg, a regular Al cup holder will be used with the aim of having maximum resolution. In the measurements made after catalysts testing (to check their structural stability after the chemical reactivity), due to small amount of material recovered (about 20 to 50 mg), samples are deposited by drop-casting on a zero-background silicon wafer.

Target: this technique is used to confirm the phase purity and to estimate crystallite size, based on the broadening of the diffraction profile (the sharper the Bragg reflections, the larger the crystallite size).

Example of PXRD patterns of PhotoCat (Ca-HAP and Co_x-HAP, benchmarks)

Figure 9. Experimental PXRD patterns of the different CaHAP and Co_xHAP samples. The simulated pattern of CaHAP is also indicated in red. Figure from Ref 7

The PXRD patterns reported in Figure 9, as an example from the literature,⁷ confirm the successful formation of HAP with hexagonal structure.

The PXRD patterns of Co₅HAP and Co₁₀HAP are very similar to the HAP pattern, although the diffraction peaks become broader, indicating lower crystallinity. Higher Co loadings, as in Co₁₅HAP and Co₂₀HAP samples, resulted in the disappearance of the HAP diffraction peaks. These data suggest that at low Co/Ca ratios, Co can be incorporated into the HAP structure with some distortion of the crystal lattice due to the ionic radius difference between Ca²⁺ and Co²⁺, while further Co addition promotes phase segregation with a lack of crystallinity.

- c) **Experimental Technique:** High Resolution Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (HR-FESEM) is carried out with a Zeiss SEM, model GeminiSEM 500. A very dilute suspension of the catalysts was prepared (>0.01mg/mL) in water with sonication and then a single drop was placed into the carbon film of a TEM grid. This grid was left covered till the drop was completely dried. Finally, the grid was placed in a special sample holder and introduced in the HR-SEM chamber for the measurement.

Target: this technique is employed to study the morphology and particle size of the samples. This last feature is fundamental, since it will affect the dispersion of the filler in the matrix to prepare the MMM.

Example of SEM analysis of a PhotoCat (Cu-HPA, benchmark)

Figure 10. HR-FESEM image of Cu-HPA.

The HR-FESEM image (Figure 10) reveals the presence of crystallites with heterogeneous morphology and size in the range of 20-150 nm, in agreement with the literature.⁸

- d) **Experimental Technique:** Inductively Coupled plasma - Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) is performed on a Varian 715-ES. Before the experiment, a known amount of sample is suspended in aqua-regia or similar acidic solution and heated to 80 °C till full disaggregation of the solid particles. Then, the solution volume is set to a certain volume with deionized water before measuring. Elemental analysis by Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) is made during the SEM analysis by means of an Oxford Instruments X-MAX detector. Sample support must be chosen carefully in advance accordingly to the elements to detect and quantify in the sample. Additionally, voltage of EDX detector is set according to the electronic level energy of the heaviest element we expect to detect in the sample.

Target: these techniques are used to investigate the metal content of the materials and their chemical composition. Moreover, only for the 2nd generation of photocatalysts EDX elemental mapping is used to evaluate the formation of heterojunction.

Example of EDX analysis of a PhotoCat (Cu-HPA, benchmark)

Figure 11 reports the elemental mapping of a specific Cu-HPA photocatalyst particle selected from a HR-FESEM image. It shows that Cu is homogeneously distributed throughout the whole particle.

Figure 11. EDX elemental mapping of Cu-HPA sample.

- e) **Experimental Technique:** UV-Vis spectroscopy (UV-Vis) is carried out with a Varian Cary 5000 spectrophotometer. Samples in powder form (dry powder) are measured in diffuse reflectance UV-Vis by means of an integrating sphere.

Target: this technique is used to optically investigate in which part of the light spectrum the photocatalysts could be active.

Example of UV-Vis spectra of PhotoCat (Cu-HPA, benchmark)

Figure 12. UV-Vis spectra of as-synthesized and calcined Cu-HPA samples. Figure from Ref. 8

- f) **Experimental Technique:** N₂ Adsorption/Desorption at 77 K (N₂@77K) is performed with a Micromeritics 3Flex sorption analyzer in the 0-1 p/p₀ range. Before each measurement,

samples (in powder form) are activated to remove the physisorbed species, by heating the materials under vacuum at a specific temperature.

Target: this technique is employed to investigate the textural properties of materials (specific surface area, SSA, Cumulative Pore Volume, CPV and Pore Size Distribution, PSD).

Example of N₂ isotherms at 77 K of PhotoCat (Cu-HPA, benchmark)

Figure 13. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms at 77 K of CuHPA sample

The adsorption/desorption isotherms of CuHPA sample are acquired with N₂ at 77 K in the 0-1 p/p₀ range (Figure 13) after activation at 423 K 1 hour under vacuum. The collected isotherm is of Type IVa (IUPAC classification).³ The material does not contain intrinsic porosity and the hysteresis loop above 0.8 of p/p₀ is related to the capillary condensation inside the interparticle voids. The BET SSA is calculated through the BET equation at p/p₀ < 0.1 is ~83 m²g⁻¹.

Advanced Characterization of fillers for MMMs

The basic characterization step is useful to identify the most promising materials that deserve to be further characterized, by applying a multi-technique, advanced characterization approach. This step will investigate the intimate physico-chemical properties of fillers (both adsorbents and photocatalysts) to really understand if they can be employed in the MMMs production.

In the following, the different advanced characterization techniques will be reported by dividing the materials in two main categories: adsorbents (MOFs or polymers) and photocatalysts.

Advanced Characterization of MOFs and insoluble Polymers – INSTM, CNR, USwan

MOFs and insoluble polymers synthesized in *Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 of WP2* are investigated to disclose their structural stability, textural properties, adsorption sites and adsorption properties. All the

advanced experimental techniques reported below will be applied exclusively to adsorbents that, after initial screening of their basic physico-chemical properties, are considered as possible candidates for the preparation of MMMs.

Thermal stability of MOFs – INSTM

The evaluation of the thermal stability of MOFs cannot be performed by simply observing the TGA profile. Indeed, being MOFs crystalline materials, it is important to evaluate the evolution of their PXRD patterns with temperature. This assessment is essential especially if the MOF will be employed in MMMs assembly that have to be used in the single module to perform both CO₂ capture and conversion. The thermal stability of the framework is evaluated between 313 and 553 K, as the maximum temperature reached in the photothermal reaction should be 473 K.

Experimental Technique: *Variable-Temperature PXRD (VT-PXRD)* was performed using an Anton Paar BTS-500 non-ambient chamber installed on the Rigaku Miniflex 600-C diffractometer.

Target: this technique is used to further assess the thermal stability of the samples up to 553 K, monitoring the diffraction profile as a function of temperature to assess the possible occurrence of phase transitions induced by loss of solvent or the loss of crystallinity upon framework collapse.

Example of VT- PXRD experiment of a MOF (Ca-squarate)

Figure 14. VT-XRD experiments of Ca-squarate

The experiment was performed with a temperature program that involves heating to the temperatures displayed in the figure at a rate of 10 K/min, waiting 10 minutes once the target temperature is reached and collecting the PXRD pattern. At the end of the heating ramp, the sample is cooled back to 313 K and a PXRD pattern is collected to monitor whether the observed changes are reversible. In the case of Ca-squarate (Figure 14), no evident changes take place in the PXRD pattern, suggesting that the MOF is stable at least up to 553 K.

Adsorption properties of MOFs and insoluble polymers – INSTM, USwan

After the investigation of the physico-chemical features of fillers used to capture CO₂, a further essential step to drive the choice of the best materials for MMMs assembly is the evaluation of their adsorption properties. For this reason, the following protocol of advanced characterization will be carried out on selected materials:

Evaluation of activation protocol - INSTM

Experimental Technique: *in-situ IR spectroscopy (in situ IR)* is performed using a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrophotometer, equipped with a MCT cryogenic detector. The resolution of the reported IR spectra was 2.0 cm⁻¹ and an average of 32 scans was used to reduce the signal to noise ratio. The sample, in form of a self-supported pellet, with an optical density of ca. 7 mg cm⁻², mechanically protected by a gold envelope, was inserted in a special home-made quartz cell with KBr windows. The cell was connected to a conventional high-vacuum glass line, that allows in situ adsorption/desorption experiments.

Target: the investigation of adsorption properties of microporous materials (as MOFs or PIMs) implies that materials undergo a proper activation step, to effectively remove pre-adsorbent species from the micropores, as water or solvents used during the synthesis procedure or the workup and by preserving at the same time their microporous framework and/or crystallinity. The evaluation of the proper activation protocol could be indicatively carried out by observing the TGA curve, however, the use of *in situ* techniques allows us to really appreciate the conditions needed to clean the adsorbent surface before adsorption experiments, minimizing the time of outgassing and the temperature of the treatment.

Example of investigation of the activation protocol by in situ IR spectroscopy of a MOF (Cu-MOF)

Figure 15. IR spectra of Cu-MOF during activation: as synthesized (black), during outgassing at room temperature (yellow sequence) and completely outgassed at 100 °C for 1 h (red).

The presence of a small fraction of water inside the MOF framework is suggested by the broad band between 3700 and 3200 cm⁻¹ in the starting spectrum (Figure 15), attributed to the stretching

vibration of the OH groups of H₂O molecules. These bands decrease in intensity by outgassing the material in vacuum under the IR beam (i.e. at a T of ~40 °C). However, after an outgassing of different hours, some weak signals ascribed to water are still present. These spectral components completely disappear by outgassing the sample at 100 °C for 1 hour. For this reason, an outgassing of 1 hour at 100 °C is selected as standard activation procedure for this material.

Evaluation of textural properties with Ar and CO₂ – INSTM, USwan

Measurements with N₂ at low T are feasible only if the probe can access the microporous structure of the MOF/polymer. If that is not the case, other adsorptive must be used for textural properties evaluation, as prescribed by IUPAC.³

Experimental Technique: *Ar and CO₂ adsorption/desorption at 87 K and 273/195 K respectively (Ar@87K, CO₂@273K and CO₂@195K)* are carried out with a Micromeritics 3Flex sorption analyzer or an Anton Paar Nova600 instrument in the 0-1 p/p₀ range. Before each measurement, samples (in powder form) are activated to remove the physisorbed species, by heating the materials under vacuum at a specific temperature (evaluated by TGA or *in situ* IR measurements).

Target: this technique is employed to investigate the textural properties of materials (specific surface area, SSA, Cumulative Pore Volume, CPV and Pore Size Distribution, PSD) if N₂ at 77 K cannot properly diffuse into the micropores, due to the well-known limits of this molecular probe: low diffusion rate due to the large kinetic diameter (0.36 nm), ellipsoidal shape, and quadrupole moment. For CPV/PSD evaluation of microporous materials, Ar and CO₂ adsorption isotherms must be collected by acquiring at least 30 points below 0.01 of p/p₀.

Example of N₂@77K versus Ar@87K adsorption on a MOF (Co-UTSA-16, benchmark)

Figure 16. N₂ at 77 K and Ar at 87 K adsorption/desorption isotherms on UTSA-16 in the 0-0.2 p/p₀ range. The inset reports a magnification of the low relative pressure range.

The comparison between the isotherms of Ar at 87 K and of N₂ at 77 K collected on standard Co-UTSA-16 (Figure 16) prove that Ar allows detecting more resolved isotherms. Indeed, it fills narrow micropores at significantly higher relative pressures in comparison with N₂ at 77 K. This leads to accelerated equilibration and permits the measurement of high-resolution adsorption isotherms.

Hence, Ar adsorption at 87 K allows a much more straightforward correlation to be obtained between the pore filling pressure and the confinement effect (depending on pore width and shape).

Example of CO₂ Adsorption at 273 K on a polymer (TAT-TB polymer)

Figure 17. TAT-TB CO₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms measured at 273 K

The CO₂ adsorption for an outgassed sample (393K, 8h) of TAT-TB polymer was measured at 273 K (Figure 17). The PSD was calculated from the adsorption at 273 K via NL-DFT method. The use of CO₂ allows the evaluation of pores with size down to 3 Å.⁹

From the calculation of the PSD (Figure 18), we can notice that the material shows a tri-modal distribution, with the first peak centred at 3.5 Å. The second series of peaks is centred between 4.4-5.7 Å. This seems the dominant distribution, shown that most of the ultramicropores are centred in this region. The last peak is located at 8.2 Å and shows that there is a certain increase in the pores size in the structure, with the last pores of roughly this dimension. Overall, the PSD seems suggesting a porous material with the regular pores centred around 5.2 Å, as both smaller and larger ones have lower intensities.

Figure 18. PSD of TAT-TB from CO₂ isotherm measured at 273 K, obtained by NL-DFT.

Evaluation of CO₂ adsorption and selectivity - INSTM

EIC Pathfinder Challenge:

Carbon dioxide and Nitrogen management and valorisation

Experimental Technique: *CO₂ adsorption/desorption at different temperatures (CO₂@T)* is carried out with a Micromeritics 3Flex sorption analyzer or an Anton Paar Nova600 instrument until 1 bar of pressure with pure CO₂. Before each measurement, samples (in powder form) are activated to remove the physisorbed species, by heating the materials under vacuum at a specific temperature (evaluated by TGA or *in situ* IR measurements). Temperatures between 273 and 363 K will be explored.

Target: this technique is employed to quantitatively investigate the capacity of MOFs and polymers to adsorb CO₂ and to explore the affinity of fillers towards N₂ and CH₄, to assess their selectivity towards the CO₂ molecule.

Experimental Technique: *Heat of Adsorption (Q_{st})* can be evaluated with the Clausius-Clapeyron approach. In this way the adsorption heat is related to the temperature dependence of the isotherms. At least three adsorption isotherms collected at different T should be fitted with the same continuous function. The adsorption enthalpy $\Delta H_{\text{ads}} = -Q_{\text{st}}$ can be then calculated from the linear regression of the $\ln(p)$ vs $1/T$ plot.¹⁰

Target: this technique allows the indirect evaluation of the heat of adsorption between the adsorbent and the CO₂, starting from the adsorption isotherms collected at different temperatures.

Example of CO₂ adsorption isotherms at different temperatures on a MOF (Ca-squarate)

Figure 19. CO₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms at different temperatures on Ca-squarate.

Adsorption of CO₂ on Ca-squarate (Figure 19) was evaluated at three different temperatures (273, 285 and 298 K) after activation at 363 K overnight under vacuum. The amount of CO₂ adsorbed at 1 bar and 273 K is $\sim 3.0 \text{ mmol g}^{-1}$ and decreases, as expected, with the temperature till 2.5 mmol g^{-1} at 298 K.

The heat of adsorption at zero coverage ($Q^{\text{ads}}_{\text{zero cov}}$) was $\sim 38 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, testifying an interaction still in the range of physisorption, but characterized by a medium-high strength. $Q^{\text{ads}}_{\text{zero cov}}$ was extrapolated by the isosteric heat curve extracted from the fitted isotherms (fit performed with a dual-site Langmuir) using the linear version of the Clausius-Clapeyron equation.

Investigation of structural and dynamic properties - CNR

Experimental Technique:

- a) Solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (SSNMR) analysis of MOFs is performed using either of two spectrometers: Bruker Avance NEO 500 spectrometer working at the Larmor frequency of 500.13 and 125.77 MHz, for ^1H and ^{13}C , respectively, equipped with a 4 mm double-channel (H/F-X) Cross Polarization/Magic Angle Spinning (CP/MAS) probe; Varian InfinityPlus 400 spectrometer working at the Larmor frequency of 399.73 and 100.51 MHz, for ^1H and ^{13}C , respectively, equipped with a 3.2 mm double-channel (H/F-X) CP/MAS probe. Spectra are recorded on powder samples of 50-90 mg.
- b) Solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (SSNMR) analysis of polymers is performed using either of two spectrometers: Bruker Avance NEO 500 spectrometer working at the Larmor frequency of 500.13 and 125.77 MHz for ^1H and ^{13}C , respectively, equipped with a 4 mm double-channel (H/F-X) Cross Polarization/Magic Angle Spinning (CP/MAS) probe; Varian InfinityPlus 400 spectrometer working at the Larmor frequency 399.73 and 100.51 MHz for ^1H and ^{13}C , respectively, equipped with a 3.2 mm double-channel (H/F-X) CP/MAS probe.
- c) Activated or CO₂-loaded samples for SSNMR (CO₂-SSNMR) measurements are prepared using a home-made cell provided with a mechanical lever operated from outside enabling the capping of the rotor without corrupting the cell atmosphere. In particular, activated samples are prepared by heating overnight under vacuum (0.1 mbar) at the appropriate temperature the MOF powder packed into the NMR rotor (4 mm external diameter) and closing the rotor under N₂ atmosphere. For the CO₂-loaded samples, the activated powder is loaded with either CO₂ or $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ (CO₂ isotopically enriched in carbon-13) at 1 bar pressure and the rotor is sealed under the gas atmosphere after the equilibrium is reached.

The following kinds of experiments are performed:

- 1) ^1H NMR experiments by direct excitation (also with background suppression) under MAS conditions to determine MOF linker structure and MOF purity. Experiments are carried out on as synthesized, activated and, in some cases, CO₂-loaded samples to determine the effect of solvent/water removal or CO₂ loading on the structure.
- 2) ^{13}C NMR experiments by direct excitation (DE) and/or cross-polarization (CP) under MAS conditions to determine material structure and purity. Experiments are carried out on as synthesized, activated and, in some cases, CO₂-loaded materials to determine the effect of solvent/water removal or CO₂ loading on the MOF structure. Spectra are also recorded on $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ loaded samples to better record the signal of physisorbed CO₂ and investigate framework-CO₂ interactions.
- 3) ^{13}C NMR experiments by direct excitation and/or cross-polarization under static or MAS conditions to investigate the status of CO₂ in the material and characterize CO₂ dynamics through line shape analysis of spectra recorded at variable temperature.
- 4) NMR experiments on NMR active metal nuclei to investigate the metal coordination in MOFs under different conditions (as synthesized, activated, CO₂ loaded).

Target: these measurements are carried out on selected MOFs and polymers to acquire information on the structural and dynamic properties at atomic level, as well as on MOF-CO₂ and polymer-CO₂ interactions and CO₂ status within material.

Example of SSNMR measurements on a MOF (Ca-squarate)

The above-reported protocol, except for the last point, is applied by the research unit to Ca-squarate. ^1H DE MAS spectra acquired on the as synthesized, activated, and CO₂-loaded MOF (Figure 20), indicate that the as synthesized MOF contains physisorbed water that can be removed by the

activation process; after activation only coordinated water remains. Upon CO₂ loading the ¹H signal is shifted indicating interactions of CO₂ with the framework.

Figure 20. ¹H DE MAS spectra of as synthesised (a), activated (b), and CO₂ loaded (c) Ca-squarate. Spectra were recorded at the spinning frequency of 15 kHz.

These results are supported by ¹³C DE MAS experiments (Figure 21). Shifts of carbon signals are observed upon physisorbed water removal and CO₂ adsorption. Moreover, the signal of adsorbed CO₂ is clearly observed in the ¹³C DE MAS spectrum.

Figure 21. ¹³C DE MAS spectra of as synthesised (a), activated (b), and (c) CO₂ loaded Ca-squarate. Spectra were recorded at the spinning frequency of 15 kHz.

Static and slow MAS ¹³C DE spectra are also acquired on a ¹³CO₂ loaded sample of Ca-squarate. As shown in Figure 22, the signal of ¹³CO₂ has an anisotropic line shape arising from the chemical shift interaction, which is only partially averaged by anisotropic motions in the framework. This indicates an interaction between the MOF and the CO₂ molecules is occurring. The line shape remains the same over the 273-313 temperature range.

Figure 22. ^{13}C DE static (a) and MAS spectra of $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ loaded Ca-squarate recorded at 298K. The MAS spectra were recorded at the spinning frequency of 2.5 kHz (b) and 15 kHz (c).

Advanced Characterization of PhotoThermal catalysts – INSTM, ITQ-UPV, CNR

Photocatalysts synthesized in Tasks 2.4 of WP2 are additionally characterized to further disclose their surface properties, and possibly correlate them with their catalytic activity. All the advanced experimental techniques reported below will be applied exclusively to photocatalysts that, after the initial screening of their basic physico-chemical properties, are considered as possible candidates for the preparation of catalytic MMMs.

Investigation of photothermal catalysts surface – INSTM, ITQ-UPV

After the investigation of the basic physico-chemical features of catalysts for CO_2 conversion, a further essential step to drive the choice of the best materials for MMMs assembly is the evaluation of their surface properties. For this reason, the following protocol of advanced characterization will be carried out on selected materials:

Evaluation of activation protocol – INSTM

Experimental Technique: *in-situ IR spectroscopy (in situ IR)* is performed using a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrophotometer, equipped with a MCT cryogenic detector. The resolution of the reported IR spectra was 2.0 cm^{-1} and an average of 32 scans was used to reduce the signal to noise ratio. The sample, in form of a self-supported pellet, with an optical density of ca. 7 mg cm^{-2} , mechanically protected by a gold envelope, was inserted in a special home-made quartz cell with KBr windows. The cell was connected to a conventional high-vacuum glass line, that allows in situ adsorption/desorption experiments.

Target: the investigation of catalytic sites with specific probe molecules implies that materials undergo a proper activation step, to effectively remove pre-adsorbent species, mainly water. The use of *in situ* techniques allows us to really appreciate the conditions needed to clean the catalyst surface before adsorption experiments, minimizing the time of outgassing and the temperature of the treatment.

Example of investigation of the activation protocol by *in situ* IR spectroscopy of a PhotoCat (Cu-HAP, benchmark)

The presence of a small fraction of water on the surface of CuHAP is suggested by the broad band between 3750 and 3000 cm^{-1} in the starting spectrum at room temperature (Figure 23), attributed to the stretching vibration of the OH groups of H_2O molecules. The band of HOH bending mode is also well evident at 1636 cm^{-1} . These bands decrease in intensity by outgassing the material in vacuum under the IR beam (*i.e.*, at a T of $\sim 40^\circ\text{C}$). These spectral components completely disappear by outgassing the sample at 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour. For this reason, an outgassing of 1 hour at 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ is selected as standard activation procedure for this material.

Figure 23. IR spectra of Cu-HAP during activation: in air (bold red), during outgassing at beam temperature (light red sequence) and completely outgassed at 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h (blue).

Study of active sites with probe molecules – INSTM, ITQ-UPV

Experimental Technique: *in-situ IR spectroscopy with probe molecules (in situ IR-probe)*, as Carbon Monoxide (CO) and CO_2 , is performed using a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrophotometer, equipped with a MCT cryogenic detector. The resolution of the reported IR spectra was 2.0 cm^{-1} and an average of 32 scans was used to reduce the signal to noise ratio. The sample, in form of a self-supported pellet, with an optical density of ca. 7 mg cm^{-2} , mechanically protected by a gold envelope, was inserted in a special home-made quartz cell with KBr windows. The cell was connected to a conventional high-vacuum glass line, that allows *in situ* adsorption/desorption experiments. Adsorption of CO with the activated material is studied by dosing a proper amount of gas (~ 60 mbar) into the cell and cooling down to 77 K with liquid nitrogen. Adsorption of CO_2 is instead followed with IR by sending in contact with the activated material incremental doses of gas at room temperature.

Target: this technique is used to investigate the catalysts' active sites. In particular, CO adsorption at the liquid nitrogen temperature, can be exploited to discriminate between sites of slightly different acidity, *i.e.*, it provides an overview of the different acid sites present on the catalyst surface, also in the presence of rather small differences in acid strength. On the other side, the adsorption of CO_2 at room temperature (or at the temperature of the reaction) followed with IR gives information about the way the molecule interacts with the catalysts' active sites, undergoing activation, possibly through the formation of carbonate-like species.

Example of CO adsorption at 77 K followed by in situ IR of a PhotoCat (Cu-HAP, benchmark)

The adsorption of CO at 77 K on the activated material (150 °C 1h in vacuum) highlights the presence of different sites (Figure 24). In particular, three main signals can be observed at 2178, 2160 and 2115 cm^{-1} , ascribable to the interaction of CO with surface P-OH groups and to the formation of Ca^{2+} -CO and Cu^{+} -CO adducts, respectively. The different components are easily detectable in the spectra collected upon CO outgassing (grey and red spectra). The interaction with Cu^{+} sites is the strongest, as the signal is less reversible than the others, by decreasing the CO pressure.

Figure 24. IR spectra of CO adsorption at 77 K on Cu-HAP in the CO stretching region: activated (blue), CO maximum coverage at 77 K (black), CO outgassing at 77 K (light grey and red sequence).

Experimental Technique: CO₂, CO and H₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms at different temperatures (CO₂@T, CO@T, H₂@T) are carried out with a Micromeritics 3Flex sorption analyzer until 1 bar of pressure with pure gases. Before each measurement, samples (in powder form) are activated to remove the physisorbed species, by heating the materials under vacuum at a specific temperature (evaluated by in situ IR measurements). Temperatures between 273 and 473 K are explored.

Target: this technique is employed to quantitatively investigate the affinity of catalysts towards CO₂ and other reaction precursors, such as H₂ or CO.

Experimental Technique: Heat of Adsorption (Q_{st}) can be evaluated with the Clausius-Clapeyron approach. In this way the adsorption heat of the different molecules is related to the temperature dependence of the isotherms. At least three adsorption isotherms collected at different T should be fitted with the same continuous function. The adsorption enthalpy $\Delta H_{\text{ads}} = -Q_{\text{st}}$ can be then calculated from the linear regression of the $\ln(p)$ vs $1/T$ plot.¹⁰

Target: this technique allows the indirect evaluation of the heat of adsorption between the catalyst and different reaction gases, starting from the adsorption isotherms collected at different temperatures.

Example of CO₂ adsorption isotherms at different temperatures on a PhotoCat (Cu-HAP, benchmark)

Adsorption of CO₂ on Cu-HAP (Figure 25) was evaluated at three different temperatures (0, 25 and 50 °C) after catalysts activation at 150 °C overnight in vacuum (evaluated by *in situ* IR

measurements). The amount of CO₂ adsorbed at 1 bar and 0 °C is ~0.6 mmol g⁻¹. However, the isotherm has not yet reached the plateau. The adsorbed amount rapidly decreases to 0.2 mmol g⁻¹ at 25 °C, but then it remains constant by increasing the temperature to 50 °C. The behaviour of the adsorption isotherms (collected consecutively at the three temperatures) testifies that a fraction of CO₂ remains irreversibly adsorbed on the catalyst surface after the first adsorption run at 0 °C. The irreversibly CO₂ adsorbed is probably in the form of carbonate-like species, as proved by the *in situ* IR experiments carried out on the materials. To remove this fraction of carbonate species, the materials should be activated at higher temperatures.

Figure 25. CO₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms at different temperatures on Cu-HPA

Experimental Technique: Temperature Programmed Desorption (TPD) with CO₂ is carried out on approximately 100 mg of sample. Catalysts is pressed till formation of a pellet that is afterwards gently crushed to form small chunks. Then, with the help of a 100 mesh sieve, pieces with the right size are selected and introduced in the reactor. Then the reactor is flushed with the desired gas at room temperature to leave the sample adsorb the reactant, after some time, the temperature start increasing while a flow of helium or argon goes through the reactor while gas composition is measured to monitor the gas release from material surface.

Target: this technique is employed to investigate the interaction strength of reactants with surface active sites of catalysts.

Example of CO₂ TPD on a PhotoCat (Cu-HAP, benchmark)

The TPD measurements reported in Figure 26, as an example from the literature,⁸ were used to characterize the adsorption strength of CO₂ at the unreduced Cu-HAP surface (Figure 26), particularly at Lewis-basic PO₄³⁻/CuO surface sites. The primary TPD event for 0 mol % Cu-HAP was centered at 250 °C, and little change occurred at the lowest Cu²⁺ content of 0.5mol % Cu. Higher Cu content induced a shift toward higher-temperature TPD events, due to the growing presence of more-basic CuO surface sites.

Figure 26. TPD curves obtained from calcined 0, 0.5, 5, 10 and 20 mol% Cu-HAP under CO₂ atmosphere. Figure from Ref. 8

Redox and photoelectronic properties of photothermal catalysts – ITQ-UPV

Another essential step to drive the choice of the best photocatalysts to produce MMMs for CO₂ conversion, is the evaluation of their redox and electronic properties. For this reason, the following protocol of advanced characterization will be carried out on selected materials:

Experimental Technique: *X-Ray Photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and in situ XPS* are carried out with a SPECS spectrometer with a MCD-9 detector using a monochromatic Al (K α = 1486.6 eV) X-ray source. Before analysis a certain amount (10 to 20 mg) of catalyst is activated under vacuum and 150 °C (evaluated by *in situ IR* measurements) to remove water and other physisorbed or chemisorbed species from the catalyst surface. *In situ XPS* measurements, to study the material behavior by changing the temperature or under light irradiation, can be also carried out. Spectra fitting is performed after Shirley subtraction of background with the CASA software using the C 1s peak at 284.4 eV as binding energy reference.

Target: this technique is used to study the oxidation state of the catalyst elements.

Example of XPS experiment performed on a PhotoCat (Cu-HAP, benchmark)

In situ Cu 2p XPS spectra reported in Figure 27, as an example from the literature,⁸. exhibit peaks attributed to Cu²⁺ sites in the HAP lattice at 932.7 and 952.4 eV for as-synthesized 0.5 and 1 mol % Cu-HAP. The peaks of as-synthesized 10 mol % Cu-HPA, as well as those of calcined 10 mol % Cu-HAP, shifted toward higher binding energies of 933.4 and 953.3 eV, corresponding to surface Cu²⁺ hydrates and CuO.

Figure 27. Cu 2p XPS spectra of as-synthesized and calcined Cu-HAP. Figure from Ref.8

Experimental Technique: Cyclovoltammetry (CV) is carried out with a Gamry Instruments potentiostat (model Interface 5000E). First, we prepare the electrode by depositing a film of the sample on top of conductive substrate such as fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO), graphite paper or metallic sheet that will act as our working electrode. To do so we could employ “doctor blade” technique to form the sample film, however other techniques such as drop-casting, spray-coating or other are also suitable. For “Doctor Blade”, a paste is prepared by making a suspension of 100 μL of α -terpineol, 10 mg of the sample and 1 mL acetone, then we leave the suspension stirring and curing at 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 h until a dense paste is obtained. Finally, the prepared films are dried at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 h. Electrochemical measurements were carried out in a single compartment and three arm quartz electrolytic cell with three electrodes using a platinum wire as counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl in 3 M KCl mixture as reference electrode. The electrolyte choice will depend on the solvent used, for instance, working in water we could use several choices such as 1 M KCl, Na_2SO_4 , NaOH, etc., in organic solvent, such as acetonitrile, we could use 0.1 M of TBAPF₆ (TBA: Tetrabutylammonium) or LiClO₄. The photocurrent is measured making pulses alternating dark and illumination and if necessary, polarizing the working electrode at potentials from 1 to 0 V. Cyclovoltammetries are measured by linear scanning of positive to negative voltages depending on the working window of the solvent. Irradiations are performed using an optical fiber connected to a Hamamatsu 150 W Hg-Xe lamp equipped with an AM 1.5G type filter.

Target: this technique is carried out to investigate the reduction and oxidation processes of catalysts.

Experimental Technique: Temperature programmed reduction (TPR). Approximately 100 mg of sample is pressed till formation of a pellet that is afterwards gently crushed to form small chunks. Then, with the help of a 100 mesh sieve, pieces with the right size are selected and introduced in the reactor. Then the reactor is pressurized with H₂ with a continuous flow and the temperature increases from room temperature to 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, while H₂ concentration is continuously measured with gas chromatography.

Target: this technique is carried out to study the reducibility of photocatalysts surface and find the most efficient reduction conditions.

Example of H₂ TPR of a PhotoCat (Co_x-HAP, benchmark)

Figure 28. H₂ TPR of CaHAP (black), Co₅HAP (green), Co₁₀HAP (blue), Co₁₅HAP (red) and Co₂₀HAP (orange). Figure from Ref. 7

TPR data reported in Figure 28, as an example from the literature,⁷ show that Co_xHAP samples exhibit weak reduction peaks at temperatures below 400 °C, while more pronounced reduction peaks appear at temperatures between 600 and 700 °C.

Experimental Technique: *Transient absorption Spectroscopy (TAS)* is performed with an OPO Ekspla (EKS-NT342C-10) laser coupled with an UV extension (EKS-NT342C-SH-SFG) as the excitation pulse and an Edinburgh Instruments detection System (LP980) coupled with an ICCD camera (Andor iStar CCD 320T). Normally, all samples are measured suspended in acetonitrile (due to lack of absorbance at most wavelengths of this solvent) after adjusting the optical absorbance to 0.4 at the desired wavelength. TAS is recorded in solution with the same optical absorbance and solvent. Chemicals in the form of gas or liquid can be employed to selectively quench transient electronic excited species generated after laser excitation. As examples, O₂ gas is purged into the cuvette as triplet excited state and electron quencher, N₂O gas is purged into the cuvette as solvated electron quencher, and methanol (200 mL) is used as hole or cation quencher.

Target: this technique is used to study the photoelectronic properties of catalysts, such as photoinduced electronic excited species or charge separation.

Morphological investigation of the active phase – ITQ-UPV

Experimental Technique: *Dark Field Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (DF-STEM)* is carried out with a JEOL JEM2100F instrument operating at 200 kV. A very diluted suspension of the catalysts is prepared in water (>0.01mg/mL) with sonication and then a single drop was placed into the carbon film of a TEM grid. This grid was left covered till the drop was completely dried and then measured with the microscope.

Target: this technique is employed to study the distribution of the active nanoparticles or co-catalysts on the substrates.

Investigation of structural properties – CNR

The study of the structural properties can add important information for the selection of the best photocatalysts for CO₂ conversion. For this reason, the following experiments will be carried out on selected materials:

Experimental Technique:

Solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (SSNMR) analysis of PhotoCat is performed using a Bruker Avance NEO 500 spectrometer working at the Larmor frequency of 500.13 and 202.46 MHz for ¹H and ³¹P, respectively, equipped with a 4 mm double-channel (H/F-X) Cross Polarization/Magic Angle Spinning (CP/MAS) probe. Spectra are recorded on powder samples of 60-90 mg. For all the samples and kinds of experiments, preliminary set up experiments are carried out to optimize parameters, such as pulse duration(s), recycle delay, number of scans, contact time value (in CP experiments), and spinning rate (in MAS experiments). Spectra are processed using Bruker TopSpin or MestreNova software.

The following kinds of experiments are performed:

- 1) ¹H NMR experiments by direct excitation (also with background suppression) under MAS conditions to determine the catalyst structure and the possible presence of water.
- 2) ³¹P NMR experiments by direct excitation (DE) and/or cross-polarization (CP) under MAS conditions to determine the catalyst structure and purity. The comparison between CP and DE spectra allows phosphorus atoms close to hydrogens to be singled out.
- 3) ³¹P NMR experiments exploiting the Hahn echo pulse sequence and/or the variable offset method to acquire broad spectra extending over thousands of ppm because of interactions of ³¹P nuclei with metal unpaired electrons.
- 4) Measurements of ³¹P longitudinal relaxation times through inversion recovery or saturation recovery experiments to determine the presence and distribution of metal atoms with unpaired electrons and the proximity of phosphorus atoms to metal atoms.

Target: these measurements are carried out on selected PhotoCat to acquire information on structural properties at the atomic level.

Examples of SSNMR measurements on PhotoCat (Cu-HPA, Co-HPA, Ru-HPA, all benchmarks)

The above-reported protocol is applied by the research unit to catalyst samples constituted by hydroxyapatite doped with transition metals (10% Cu, Co or Ru; samples indicated as UPV-CuHAP, UPV-CoHAP, and UPV-RuHAP, respectively). In particular, ¹H DE MAS spectra reveal the presence of adsorbed water (4.8 or 5.7 ppm) and show signals typical of hydroxyapatite (0.3 or 0.5 ppm) for Cu and Ru doped samples, while signals are broadened and shifted by the interaction of ³¹P nuclear spins with unpaired electron spins for the Co doped sample (Figure 29).

Figure 29. ^1H DE MAS spectra of hydroxyapatite doped with Cu (a), Ru (b), and Co (c). The spectra were recorded at the spinning frequency of 15 kHz.

As far as ^{31}P NMR experiments are concerned, Cu and Ru doped samples were investigated by recording DE MAS and ^1H - ^{31}P CP MAS spectra. For comparison a spectrum was also recorded on a sample of undoped hydroxyapatite (UPV-CaHAP). As shown in Figure 30, UPV-CuHAP and UPV-RuHAP exhibit signals typical of hydroxyapatite (3.2 – 3.5 ppm) and pyrophosphates (-10.2, -8.5 ppm). The spectral integral intensity of quantitative spectra of UPV-CuHAP and UPV-RuHAP is 70 and 90% of that of undoped hydroxyapatite, indicating that part of ^{31}P nuclei show undetectable broad signals because of the effect of the metal unpaired electrons.

Figure 30. ^{31}P DE MAS spectra of hydroxyapatite (a) and hydroxyapatite doped with Cu (b) and Ru (c). The spectra were recorded at the spinning frequency of 15 kHz.

For the Co doped sample, the broad ^{31}P spectrum resulting from the hyperfine interaction of the ^{31}P nuclei with the Co unpaired electrons was acquired using the Hahn echo pulse sequence at variable offsets, as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31. ^{31}P spectrum of hydroxyapatite doped with Co (UPV-CoHAP) recorded using the Hahn echo pulse sequence at variable offsets.

^{31}P longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) values were measured on UPV-CuHAP, UPV-CoHAP, and UPV-RuHAP samples using the saturation recovery pulse sequence. For UPV-CuHAP a stretched exponential function could reproduce the magnetization trend with $T_1 = 73$ ms and exponent 0.40 for hydroxyapatite phosphorus nuclei and $T_1 = 11.7$ ms and exponent 0.39 for pyrophosphate phosphorus nuclei. For UPV-RuHAP a stretched exponential function could reproduce the magnetization trend with $T_1 = 29.3$ s and exponent 0.56 for all phosphorus nuclei. In the case of UPV-CoHAP, a monoexponential trend of magnetization was observed with $T_1 = 147$ ms.

It must be pointed out that the applied protocol may change according to the NMR-active nuclei and paramagnetic metal present in the catalyst sample.

Tables of ongoing Characterization experiments

In this section, the tables reporting the characterization activities (both basic and advanced) **carried out until month 9 on the different DAM4CO₂ materials**, synthesized in WP2, will be listed and divided by sample categories (MOFs, polymers and photocatalysts). **In these tables, the materials synthesized as benchmarks will be listed as well.** Indeed, especially in the catalytic section, the understanding of photocatalysts to be used as references is crucial for the development of other catalysts based of non-critical raw materials.

Table 1: Basic Characterization of MOFs synthesized in WP2

Material	PXRD	TGA	ICP-OES	SEM	N2@77K	PSD
Zr-fumarate (MIP-203)	✓				✓	✓
Zr-fumarate (MOF-801)	✓		✓		✓	✓
Zr-succinate (MIP-203)	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Zr-fumarate (MIP-203 - Acetic Acid)	✓			✓	✓	
Zr-fumarate (A.A)	✓				✓	
Zr-fumarate/succinate mixed MOF	✓	✓			✓	
L-Aspartate(Al)	✓				✓	
Ca-squarate	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Zr-squarate	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Ca-trimesate	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Zn/K-citrate	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓

Table 2: Basic Characterization of Monomeric precursors and Polymers synthesized in WP2

Material	¹ H NMR	¹³ C NMR	IR	N ₂ @77 K	PSD	TGA
DNT (Monomer)	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
DAT (Monomer)	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
TNT (Monomer)	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
BMA (Monomer)	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
DN-BMA (Monomer)	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
DA-BMA (Monomer)	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
DAT (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TAT (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
6FDA-DAM (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓		✓
PIM-1 (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
DABMA (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TPB-HC (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TRIP-HC (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TPB-HSO3 (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TRIP-HSO3 (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TPB-NO2 (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
TRIP-NO2 (Polymer)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3: Basic Characterization of *Photothermal catalysts* synthesized in WP2

Materials	IR	PXRD	HR-FESEM	ICP-OES	EDX	UV-Vis	N ₂ @77 K
UPV-CuHAP1*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UPV-CoHPA1*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UPV-RuHPA1*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UPV-NiTiAl-LDH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-CoTiAl-LDH*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-NiCoTiAl-LDH*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-NiTiAl-OH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-Cu/MnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV- CaHPA2*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-NiAl-LDH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-NiAlOx_Project	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UPV-Ni/NiO Sigma**	✓	✓	✓				
UPV-Fe/Co-G(N)*	✓	✓	✓				

*Materials synthesized in WP2 as Benchmarks

** Commercial material

Table 4: Advanced Characterization of selected MOFs synthesized in WP2

Material	VTPXRD	¹ H MAS NMR	¹³ C MAS NMR	¹³ C static NMR	In situ IR	Ar@87K, CO2@273K CO2@195K	CO2@T Qst
Ca-squarate	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Ca-trimesate	✓	✓	✓			✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Zr-squarate	✓	✓	✓			✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Zn/K-citrate	✓					✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Zr-fumarate MIP-203		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Zr-succinate MIP-203		✓	✓			✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Zr-malate MIP-203		✓	✓			✓(CO2@273K)	✓
Zr-fumarate MIP-801		✓	✓		✓	✓(CO2@273K)	✓

Table 5: Advanced Characterization of Polymers synthesized in WP2

Material	¹ H MAS NMR	¹³ C MAS NMR	¹³ C static NMR	In situ IR	Ar@87K, CO2@273K CO2@195K	CO2@T Qst
PIM-EA-TB	✓	✓			✓(CO2@273K)	✓
PIM-1-Trip-NO2	✓	✓	✓		✓(CO2@273K)	✓
PIM-1-Trip-HSO3	✓	✓			✓(CO2@273K)	✓

Table 6: Advanced Characterization of Photothermal catalysts synthesized in WP2

Material	DF-STEM	XPS	CV	TAS	TPR	TPD	¹ H MAS NMR	³¹ P MAS NMR	T ₁ meas.	In situ IR	In situ IR-probe	CO2 @T
UPV-CuHAP1*	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UPV-CoHPA1*	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV-RuHPA1*							✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UPV- CaHPA2*	✓	✓			✓			✓				
UPV-Ni/NiO Sigma**							✓			✓	✓	

*Materials synthesized in WP2 as Benchmarks

** Commercial material

References

- ¹ Robl, C. *et al.*, *Mat. Res. Bull.* , **1987**, 22 (3), 373-380 (10.1016/0025-5408(87)90055-9)
- ² Hsu, C-H. *et al.* , *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* , **2023**, 62(39), e202309874 (10.1002/anie.202309874)
- ³ Thommes, M. *et al.* , *Pure and Applied Chem.*, **2015**, 87(9-10), 1051-1069 (10.1515/pac-2014-1117)
- ⁴ Gaikwad, S. *et al.* *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, **2020**, 87, 250-263 (10.1016/j.jiec.2020.04.015)
- ⁵ Budd, P.M., *et al.* , *Adv. Mat.*, **2004**, 16(5), 456-459 (10.1002/adma.200306053)
- ⁶ McKeown, N. B. *et al.*, *Macromolecules*, **2010**, 43, 5163-5176 (<https://doi.org/10.1021/ma1006396>)
- ⁷ Peng, J. *et al.*, *Appl. Cat. B: Envir. Ener.* , **2023**, 333, 122790 (10.1016/j.apcatb.2023.122790)
- ⁸ Guo, J. *et al.*, *ACS Catal.* , 2020, 10(22), 13668-13681 (10.1021/acscatal.0c03806)
- ⁹ Cychosz, K.A. *et al.*, *Engineering*, **2018**, 4(4), 559- doi.org/10.1016/j.eng.2018.06.001 566 (10.1016/j.eng.2018.06.001)
- ¹⁰ Nuhnen, A. *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.* , **2020**, 49(30), 10295-10307 (10.1039/D0DT01784A)

Acknowledgements

The DAM4CO₂ has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101115488. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant numbers 10083164 and 10091537]